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ABSTRACT

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DETERMINATION OF THE CHEMICAL AND MATERIAL COMPOSITION OF DROSS GENERATED DURING THE MELTING OF ZINC CATHODES

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Abstract: This study examines the chemical and oxide composition of zinc dross formed during the melting of zinc cathodes at the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Complex using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis. The results show that the dross is mainly composed of zinc (up to 90.2 wt.%) and zinc oxide (ZnO, 93.3 wt.% in oxide form), along with minor amounts of S, Cl, Fe, Mn, Si, and Ca compounds. The presence of iron and other metal oxides suggests the formation of complex phases such as zinc ferrite, which can influence hydrometallurgical processing efficiency. Overall, zinc dross is confirmed as a valuable secondary raw material with high potential for zinc recovery through pyrometallurgical or hydrometallurgical methods.

Keywords: zinc dross, XRF analysis, zinc oxide, hydrometallurgy, pyrometallurgy, zinc recovery, metallurgical waste.

Introduction. The non-ferrous metallurgy industry is one of the key sectors of modern industry, and zinc production processes occupy a particularly important place within it. Zinc is one of the most widely used metals, mainly applied for protecting steel and iron products from corrosion, producing alloys, and manufacturing various compounds in the chemical industry. At the same time, zinc production processes generate numerous by-products and wastes, one of which is zinc dross [1].

Zinc dross is mainly formed during pyrometallurgical processes, particularly during smelting and galvanizing operations, and is characterized as a complex solid phase containing metallic zinc, its oxides, and various impurities. Despite the high zinc content in this waste, it is often insufficiently processed or not fully utilized due to the lack of efficient technologies. As a result, valuable metal losses occur, economic efficiency decreases, and environmental problems arise [2].

Currently, the introduction of resource-saving and low-waste technologies in the metallurgical industry is considered one of the most pressing issues. From this

perspective, the deep processing of zinc dross, the maximum recovery of valuable components contained within it, and the development of environmentally safe technologies are of great scientific and practical importance. In particular, transferring zinc from the dross into solutions using hydrometallurgical and combined methods, followed by its recovery through electrolysis, is regarded as one of the promising approaches [3].

The purpose of this study is to analyze the composition of zinc dross, the mechanism of its formation, and modern methods for its processing, as well as to improve the efficiency of zinc recovery through the enhancement of existing technologies.

Materials and Methods. To determine the elemental composition of zinc dross generated at the zinc plant of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Complex, X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis was carried out (Table 1). The obtained results demonstrated the predominance of zinc as the main component in the sample, with its content reaching 90.2 wt.%. This confirms that zinc dross is a secondary raw material with high metallic value [4-7].

According to the analysis results, in addition to zinc, the sample also contains a number of additional elements reflecting the characteristics of the technological process. In particular, the presence of Cl (1.86 wt.%) and S (1.85 wt.%) indicates the involvement of chloride and sulfide/sulfate compounds in the zinc production process. These components may enter the dross composition, especially during hydrometallurgical stages or from the raw materials themselves [8].

Results and Discussion. The elements Si (0.166 wt.%), Ca (0.089 wt.%), and K (0.0536 wt.%) identified in the sample are mainly associated with gangue minerals or flux materials (such as lime and silica-containing additives), forming the inorganic part of the dross composition. These components influence slag formation during the processing of zinc dross [9].

Table 1. Chemical composition of zinc dross based on XRF analysis

Analyzed result(FP method, Scatter)

No.	Component	Result	Unit	Stat. Err.	LLD	LLQ
1	Cl	1.86	mass%	0.0026	0.0028	0.0085
2	Si	0.166	mass%	0.0028	0.0038	0.0113
3	S	1.85	mass%	0.0036	0.0029	0.0087
4	K	0.0536	mass%	0.0025	0.0040	0.0121
5	Ca	0.0890	mass%	0.0022	0.0023	0.0070
6	Cr	0.0023	mass%	0.0002	0.0004	0.0012
7	Mn	0.0793	mass%	0.0028	0.0043	0.0130
8	Fe	0.0657	mass%	0.0022	0.0038	0.0113
9	Ni	0.0086	mass%	0.0010	0.0025	0.0076
10	Zn	90.2	mass%	0.246	0.0003	0.0010
11	Zr	0.268	mass%	0.0049	0.0017	0.0051
12	Pb	0.0181	mass%	0.0017	0.0022	0.0065
13	Dy	0.0367	mass%	0.0046	0.0121	0.0364

Spectrum

Fig. 1. XRF spectra of dross obtained from the zinc plant of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Complex

As metallic impurities, the elements Fe (0.0657 wt.%), Mn (0.0793 wt.%), Ni (0.0086 wt.%), and Cr (0.0023 wt.%) were identified. These elements may form intermetallic compounds with zinc (for example, Fe–Zn phases), which particularly contribute to the formation of bottom dross. The presence of iron originates either from the technological equipment or from the raw materials, and it plays an important role in the processing of dross.

In addition, the detection of Pb (0.0181 wt.%) indicates the presence of lead as an accompanying element in the zinc production process. Lead usually passes into the

melt together with zinc and may subsequently accumulate in the dross composition. This requires its separate removal during further processing stages.

Although present in small amounts, elements such as Zr (0.268 wt.%) and Dy (0.0367 wt.%) are likely associated with technogenic or raw-material sources, and their presence indicates that the dross represents a complex multicomponent system.

The results of spectral analysis (spectrum) also confirmed the presence of the above-mentioned elements, particularly demonstrating the high intensity of zinc-related peaks. This once again proves the predominance of zinc as the main phase in the sample.

In general, the obtained results indicate that zinc dross is a complex technogenic product containing a high amount of metallic zinc together with various impurity elements. Therefore, the efficient processing of zinc dross for zinc recovery and the extraction of additional elements is economically and environmentally justified. In particular, the high zinc content (more than 90%) demonstrates that processing the dross by pyrometallurgical or hydrometallurgical methods is a promising and effective approach.

In order to determine the phase and chemical characteristics of zinc dross generated at the zinc plant of the Almylyk Mining and Metallurgical Complex, its oxide composition was analyzed using the X-ray fluorescence (XRF) method (Table 2). The obtained results revealed the absolute predominance of zinc oxide (ZnO) as the main component in the sample, with its content reaching 93.3 wt.%. This indicates that the major part of the zinc dross consists of oxidized zinc and has undergone a high degree of oxidation processes.

According to the analysis results, SO_3 (4.03 wt.%) was identified as an important additional component in the sample. This suggests the possible presence of sulfate compounds in the dross composition, particularly ZnSO_4 or other metal sulfates. The presence of sulfate components may result from hydrometallurgical processes or from the oxidation of SO_2 in the gas phase.

Table 2. Oxide composition of zinc dross based on XRF analysis

Analyzed result(FP method, Scatter)

No.	Component	Result	Unit	Stat. Err.	LLD	LLQ
1	Cl	1.62	mass%	0.0023	0.0025	0.0074
2	SiO ₂	0.324	mass%	0.0051	0.0057	0.0170
3	SO ₃	4.03	mass%	0.0078	0.0061	0.0182
4	K ₂ O	0.0561	mass%	0.0026	0.0042	0.0127
5	CaO	0.108	mass%	0.0027	0.0028	0.0085
6	Cr ₂ O ₃	0.0029	mass%	0.0002	0.0005	0.0015
7	MnO	0.0850	mass%	0.0031	0.0051	0.0153
8	Fe ₂ O ₃	0.0779	mass%	0.0027	0.0048	0.0145
9	NiO	0.0090	mass%	0.0011	0.0028	0.0084
10	ZnO	93.3	mass%	0.352	0.0004	0.0011
11	ZrO ₂	0.303	mass%	0.0055	0.0019	0.0058
12	PbO	0.0162	mass%	0.0015	0.0020	0.0059
13	Dy ₂ O ₃	(0.0351)	mass%	0.0045	0.0120	0.0361

Spectrum

Fig. 2. XRF spectra of the oxide composition of dross obtained from the zinc plant of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Complex

The components SiO₂ (0.324 wt.%), CaO (0.108 wt.%), and K₂O (0.0561 wt.%) identified in the sample are mainly associated with gangue minerals present in the raw materials as well as technological additives (fluxes), forming the inert (less reactive) part of the dross composition. These oxides influence slag formation during subsequent processing stages.

As oxide forms of metallic impurities, Fe₂O₃ (0.0779 wt.%), MnO (0.0850 wt.%), NiO (0.0090 wt.%), and Cr₂O₃ (0.0029 wt.%) were identified. These components may form complex phases together with zinc, and in particular, the presence of iron oxide indicates the possible formation of zinc ferrite (ZnFe₂O₄). This

is an important factor in the hydrometallurgical processing of dross because ferrite phases are difficult to dissolve in acids.

In addition, the presence of PbO (0.0162 wt.%) indicates that lead exists in the dross composition in oxide form. This confirms that lead transfers into the dross as an accompanying element during the zinc production process and should therefore be taken into account during subsequent separation stages.

One of the interesting findings was the presence of rare oxides such as ZrO_2 (0.303 wt.%) and Dy_2O_3 (0.0351 wt.%), which may be associated with the source of raw materials or technogenic impurities. These elements further confirm the complex and multicomponent nature of the dross composition.

Furthermore, Cl (1.62 wt.%) was identified in the sample, indicating the presence of chloride compounds. Chloride ions, particularly in hydrometallurgical processes, may significantly influence solution chemistry.

Conclusion. The XRF analysis results demonstrate that zinc dross mainly consists of zinc oxide, while also containing sulfates, chlorides, and various metal oxides, forming a complex multicomponent system. The high content of ZnO makes the dross a favorable raw material for hydrometallurgical processing methods, such as leaching in sulfuric acid followed by zinc recovery through electrolysis. At the same time, the necessity of preliminary removal of iron and other impurities plays an important role in optimizing the technological process.

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